

Syntheses of (*E*)-4-(2-(4-methoxyphenyl)diazenyl)benzene 1,3-diol and (*E*)-1-(2-(4-hydroxyphenyl)diazenyl)-2-naphthol and their application as acid base indicator and in jute dyeing

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Abstract : Two novel azo-dyes namely (*E*)-4-(2-(4-methoxyphenyl)diazenyl)benzene 1,3-diol (L^1) and (*E*)-1-(2-(4-hydroxyphenyl)diazenyl)-2-naphthol (L^2) have been synthesized by the usual method of diazotisation followed by coupling reaction at pH 7.5. The synthesized dyes are characterized by elemental analysis and UV-Vis, IR, ¹H NMR, mass spectrophotometry. These synthesised compounds are found to exhibit significant dyeing property on bleached jute substrate under neutral and particularly basic pH condition with good colour yield and wash fastness. Moreover the acid base indicator property of L^2 being more prominent than that of L^1 , the parameters measuring the performance of the former as an indicator have also been evaluated spectrophotometrically and conductometrically in this paper. The study shows better performance of L^2 than methyl orange, particularly for titration of dilute solutions.

The antibacterial activity of both L^1 and L^2 has also been studied, where L^2 showed more significant effect than L^1 .

Keywords : Azo-dye, jute dyeing, acid-base indicator, antibacterial effect.

Introduction

Till date azo-dyes are considered to be an important class of aromatic compounds that have been utilizing for long time, as successful colourants in textile industry. About 45,000 azo-dyes were enlisted in Colour Index¹. Out of these, 6000 azo-dyes were reported to be non-carcinogen². Among these, some are only used in textile industry and only few are applied in analytical and biochemical fields. The azo-dyes being often tailored with various aromatic moieties, possess strong electronic absorption and emission properties. These properties also gradually change with the change of solvent where these are readily soluble. They also show changes of colour at acidic and alkaline pH because of the transformation of one coloured form to another at a certain pH and it is found in a few cases that some selected azo-dyes in approx 90% purified form can be used as successful acid-base indicator³. Azo dyes cover a major area in dyeing in industry and particularly jute, because of their simplicity

of synthesis, colour intensity and cost effectivity. Jute, on the other hand, being an important biodegradable fibre, has created renewed interest for its application to decorative and value added products. So the present work involves the synthesis of L^1 (brilliant red) and L^2 (deep chocolate) dyes and their use in jute dyeing and analytical purposes. Both the compound contain azo group as chromophore and two OH groups as auxochrome. L^1 however contains an additional auxochrome OCH₃ group. Because of the presence of these auxochromes the electron density of the benzene rings may increase causing their antibacterial activity. The success of using our previously synthesized similar azo dyes⁴⁻⁸ in jute fibres and analytical purposes also motivate us to synthesize these azo dyes.

Experimental

Chemicals : All the chemicals are of analytical grade (purity around 99%) from either BDH (England) or E.

Merck (India). For the synthesis of L¹ and L² the chemicals used are 4-aminophenol, *p*-anisidine 99% ethanol (China), 2-naphthol, resorcinol, sodium nitrite, sodium hydroxide, concentrated hydrochloric acid (12 N 35%) and tetrahydrofuran. For indicator properties methyl orange and phenolphthalein were used.

Fabric : A plain weave grey jute fabric having following specification was used : Warp : 65 ends/dm (count, 152 tex); Weft : 71 ends/dm (count, 160 tex); Fabric mass; 220 g/sq. m (at 65% RH and 30 °C).

Preparation of (E)-4-(2-(4-methoxyphenyl)diazonyl)-benzene 1,3 diol⁴⁻⁸ (L¹) :

p-Anisidine (0.01 mol) was taken in a 70 ml ice cold (0–5 °C) bath and 20–25 drops of concentrated HCl 12 (N) was added dropwise till the substrate was completely dissolved. This solution was kept in a freezing mixture and diazotized by dropwise slow addition of cold (0 °C) dilute solution of sodium nitrite (0.01 mol) followed by dilution with cold (0 °C) distilled water to maintain the pH at 4–5. The cold diazotized solution was then added dropwise with stirring to ice cold (0 °C) alkaline solution of resorcinol (0.01 mol) dissolved in 130 ml of 0.7% NaOH solution. The resultant mixture was acidified with ice-cold (2 N) HCl when a brilliant red dye was obtained. It was filtered through suction, washed thoroughly with chilled water till it free from acid, then recrystallized by absolute alcohol. Purity was examined in a mixture of 5% water-ethyl alcohol by TLC with Kieselgel 60HF₂₅₄ (Kocaokutgen and Ozkinali, 2004). The yield was 2.51 g showing 83% conversion.

Preparation of (E)-1-(2-(4-hydroxyphenyl)diazonyl)-2-naphthol⁴⁻⁸ (L²) :

The method of preparation of MBADB was repeated for the preparation of HBAN using the substrate 4-amino phenol (0.01 mol) in concentrated (12 N) HCl solution (pH 2–3) which was diazotized with sodium nitrite (0.01 mol) followed by reaction with alkaline solution of 2-naphthol (0.01 mol) at ice cold condition (0–5 °C). The resultant solution was acidified with 2 (N) HCl when a brilliant chocolate red coloured dye was obtained. It was filtered, washed thoroughly and subjected to TLC for examining purity as before. The yield was 81%.

Bleaching of jute fabric : Conventional bleaching of

grey jute fabric was performed⁴⁻⁶ in a closed vessel containing hydrogen peroxide (2 vol), tri sodium phosphate (5 g/L), sodium hydroxide (1 g/L), sodium silicate (10 g/L) and nonionic detergent, Ultravon JU (2 g/L) for 2 h at 90 °C with a material to liquor ratio 1 : 20. The pH of the bath was maintained at 10. After bleaching, the fibre samples were washed thoroughly in cold water, neutralized with acetic acid (2 ml/L), washed again in cold water and finally dried.

Dyeing of bleached jute fabric : Dye bath was made with the dissolved dye (4% w/v), sodium hydroxide (1 g/L) and sodium sulphate (5 g/L) and the material to liquor ratio was kept at 1 : 20. The bleached jute fabric sample was dipped into the dye bath⁴⁻⁶, temperature slowly increased to 80 °C and dyeing was continued at that temperature for one hour. Thereafter, the sample was washed thoroughly with cold water, soaped with Ultravon JU (2 g/L) in a bath containing water (material to liquor ratio, 1 : 20) at 50 °C for 15 min followed by washing thoroughly with cold water and drying in air.

Determination of the physico-chemical properties of L¹ and L² :

Melting points of dyes L¹ and L² were measured on electrically operated melting point apparatus of Sunder Industrial Products, Mumbai, India without calibration. The UV-Vis absorption spectra were recorded in Perkin-Elmer Lambda 40 (UV-Vis) spectrophotometer in ethanol. The infrared spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer RX I FT-IR spectrophotometer with KBr discs (4000–400 cm⁻¹). Elemental analyses (C, H, N, O) were carried out using a Perkin-Elmer 2400 II elemental analyser.

The ¹H NMR spectra were on a Bruker 300 MHz FT-NMR spectrometer using trimethyl silane as an internal standard in CDCl₃ for dyes MBADB and HBAN. LC-MS Thermo Finnegan navigator 30019 was used for recording the mass spectra.

The Spectrascan-5100^R computerized colour matching system was used to measure the λ_{max}, reflectance and *K/S* values of dyed jute fabric samples using the following formula^{4,5} :

$$K/S = [(1 - R)^2/2R] \propto C$$

where *K*, the coefficient of absorption, *S* the coefficient of scattering, *R* the reflectance of substrate at λ_{max} and *C*

concentration of dye. The *K/S* value is an index of dye uptake.

Determination of the physico-chemical properties of dyed fabrics :

Rubbing, washing and light fastness were determined using ISO-105-AO3, ISO-105-AO2, ISO-105-BO1 methods (International standard ISO-105-AO3, 105-AO2-1978 and 105-BOI-1978). The exhaustion (%) and realization (%) of the dyed samples were determined as per the method described in the literature (Kaur and Singh, 2007).

The R_f values of different samples were taken on thin layer chromatography (TLC) using benzyl alcohol-dimethyl formamide-water (3 : 2 : 2) as eluent and silica gel as absorbent.

Kinetics of azo dye oxidation : Organisms (5 to 30 μ g), dialyzed against 10 mM phosphate (pH 6.5), was incubated with an azo dye (50 μ M) in 10 mM phosphate buffer (pH 6.5; 1 ml) saturated with oxygen. Dye oxidation was determined by monitoring the loss of absorbance at λ_{max} with a spectrophotometer.

Indicator properties : All glass apparatus used are of Borosil-stdA.

Conductometer used has the specification Elico, CM 180, conductivity meter and pH meter used has the specification Elico, LI 614, pH analyser.

Results and discussion

Physical properties (m.p. and elemental analysis) of L^1 and L^2 :

From data recorded in Table 1, it is clear to note that in each case single spot is located in TLC indicating high purity of the dye supported by percent error in elemental analysis within 5%.

*Structure elucidation (*E*)-4-(2-(4-methoxyphenyl)diazanyl)-benzene 1,3-diol (L^1) through FT-IR :*

From observed IR spectrum, it is suggested that L^1

should have one free -OH band⁷ (3753.64 cm^{-1} as a weak sharp stretching band) and one hydrogen bonded OH band (3456.82 cm^{-1} as a broad band). Again the figure shows a strong band at 1213.55, 1171.02, 1111.45, 1030.87 cm^{-1} which are in conformity with the characteristic band for C-O stretching as mixed band of alkyl C-O and aryl C-O stretching.

It is probable that the ligand L^1 being an unsymmetrical ether, the two C-O bonds coupled to give antisymmetric and symmetric C-O stretching absorption for which three different IR band have appeared.

The band appearing at 1471.27, 1435.49 cm^{-1} will correspond to the presence of N=N (azo) in bending frequency. The stretching frequency of N=N is absent as it is IR inactive. From literature⁹ it is also known aromatic C=C band should appear between 1500–1600 cm^{-1} , recognized at 1511.97 and 1604.90 cm^{-1} . A band appearing at 2929.70 cm^{-1} is very close to the ArC-H band of theoretically known to be 3030 cm^{-1} . So on an average the IR stretching and bending as located in the IR spectrum roughly support the presence of functional groups in our synthesized dye L^1 .

*Structure elucidation (*E*)-1-(2-(4-hydroxyphenyl)diazanyl)-2-naphthol (L^2) through FT-IR :*

The band missing from 1100 to 1000 cm^{-1} from the spectrum of L^2 does not contained any ether linkage. However the band appearing at 1501.91 cm^{-1} may correspond to azo N=N. The presence of aromatic C=C in the ligand L^2 may be due to the band 1501.91 cm^{-1} . The band 1593.72 cm^{-1} may also be associated with the presence of aromatic C=C. Again comparable medium broad band at 3172 cm^{-1} should however be due to the presence of little hydrogen bonded¹⁰ phenolic -OH. It is also suspected that the ArC-H band might be shifted to 2927.91 cm^{-1} . The presence of N=N in L^2 is difficult to explain from direct IR band which however might appear at 1375.47 cm^{-1} . So finally we conclude that L^2 should

Table 1. Elemental data for synthesized dyes, L^1 and L^2

Name of dyes	Empirical formula	Yield (%)	m.p. (°C)	R_f	Mol wt.	Analysis (%) : Calcd. (Found)			
						C	H	N	O
L^1	$C_{13}H_{12}N_2O_3$	83	189	0.76	244	63.93 (64.12)	4.95 (5.03)	11.47 (11.04)	19.65 (19.83)
L^2	$C_{16}H_{12}N_2O_2$	81	201	0.84	264	72.72 (73.12)	4.58 (4.62)	10.60 (10.69)	12.11 (11.97)

Table 2. Structure elucidation of L¹ and L² using ¹H NMR and mass spectroscopy^{7,10,11}

Name of dyes	NMR signals	Mass spectrum (<i>m/z</i>)
	¹ H NMR (δ /ppm)	
<i>(E)</i> -4-(2-(4-Methoxyphenyl)-diazenyl)benzene 1,3-diol (L ¹)	4.95 (1H, s, OH)	M-245.18 (C ₁₃ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ₃ ⁺)
	7.25 (1H, d, <i>J</i> 6 Hz, Ar-H)	M-246.18 (C ₁₃ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₃ ⁺)
	7.79–7.65 (4H, m, Ar-H)	M-242.36 (C ₁₃ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₃ ⁺)
	7.59–7.53 (1H, m, Ar-H)	M-123.10 (C ₆ H ₅ NO ₂ ⁺)
	7.41–7.36 (1H, m, Ar-H)	M-103.98 (C ₆ H ₅ N ₂ ⁺)
	7.04–6.93 (3H, m, Ar-H)	
	3.85 (3H, s, O-CH ₃)	
<i>(E)</i> -1-(2-(4-Hydroxyphenyl)-diazenyl)-2-naphthol (L ²)	4.5–4.8 (1H, s, OH)	M-279.16 (C ₁₆ H ₁₀ N ₂ O ₂ ⁺ ·H ₂ O)
	7.18 (2H, d, <i>J</i> 4.5 Hz, Ar-H)	M-287.14 (C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ Na ⁺)
	7.55–7.60 (2H, t, <i>J</i> 15 Hz, Ar-H)	M-263.18 (C ₁₆ H ₁₁ N ₂ O ₂ ⁺)
	6.9–7.08 (2H, d, <i>J</i> 9 Hz, Ar-H)	M-248.15 (C ₁₆ H ₁₂ N ₂ O ⁺)
	7.7–7.8 (4H, d, <i>J</i> 30 Hz, Ar-H)	M-156.09 (C ₁₀ H ₇ ONa ⁺)
		M-128.08 (C ₁₀ H ₈)

have the functional groups as described in molecular structure.

From the above Table 2, we confirm the molecular structure of L¹ and L² as described below.

(E)-1-(2-(4-Hydroxyphenyl)diazenyl)-2-naphthol (L²)

Dyeing properties of the L¹ and L² :

The comparative *K/S* value of these dyes^{4,5} as re-

corded in Table 4 suggest that the dye uptake of L² is sufficiently higher than that of L¹. The performance of these azodye on bleached jute fabric and the rate of oxidation (antibacterial activity) is shown in the Table 4.

Absorption maxima (λ_{\max}), intensity ($\log \epsilon$), charge transfer ($h\nu_{\text{ICT}}$), exhaustion (*E*) and fixation (*F*) of synthesized dyes on jute in shown in Table 3.

Explanation : The two dyes L¹ and L² have some difference in molecular structure and this corresponds to little different in λ_{\max} and dye exhaustion property. Again some little different in λ_{\max} between dye solution and dyed fabric has been observed which might be done to some influence of bleached jute fabric on λ_{\max} of dyed fabric. The colour yield of the dyed fabric measured by *K/S* value is directly related to % of dye exhaustion (%*E*). A low value of *K/S* is associated with low %*E*. From Tables 3 and 4, it is clear that L² has better %*E* and higher *K/S* than L¹. The % wash fastness in dye L² is also fairly higher than L¹. This is possibly not due to

Table 3. Dyeing properties of the L¹ and L²

Name of dyes	Absorption maxima		$\log \epsilon$	$h\nu_{\text{ICT}}$ (eV)	Dyeing of jute	
	In ethanol (λ_{\max} nm)	(ϵ) (M ⁻¹ cm ⁻¹)			% <i>E</i>	% <i>F</i>
L ¹	469.5	30923	4.4903	2.64	82.3	90.1
L ²	486.0	27750	4.4433	2.55	86.0	96.8

Table 4. Antibacterial activity of L¹ and L²

Name of dyes	K/S values	Rate of oxidation (Antibacterial activity)				
		Control	<i>Swmonellatyphi</i>	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>
L ¹	7.041	1.57	2.79(-)	2.78(-)	2.81(-)	2.93(-)
L ²	9.027	1.04	2.41(-)	2.37(-)	2.44(-)	2.37(-)

Diameter of incubation zone : 15 mm : concentration of bacterial growth 200 µg/mL, in DMSO solution(-) : Inactive.

phenolic -OH group orientation in the two dyes but might be due to presence of naphtha moiety in L¹. This behavior parallels with the similar commercial product chlorantine Fast Orange TGLI (CI Direct orange dye, constitution no. 40215) a direct class of dye produced by Hindustan¹².

Explanation : The data in the above Table is a clear indication of inhibition in bacterial growth of both L¹ and L². In L², it can be attributed to the fact that enriched electron cloud of naphtha moiety⁶ arising from electron donating power of phenolic oxygen center could actually be drifted to nearby vacant π^* orbital of azo(N=N) group (Spadaro and Ranganathan, 1994). In a similar manner, the electron density in benzene rings of L¹ has been enriched by donor -OCH₃ and -OH. It means that the rate of antibacterial activity^{5,13} both the dyes was fairly pronounced. However L² has better antibacterial activity than L¹. Delocalisation of the π cloud in each case is represented below.

(*E*)-4-(2-(4-Methoxyphenyl)diazenyl)benzene 1,3-diol (L¹)

(*E*)-1-(2-(4-Hydroxyphenyl)diazenyl)-2-naphthol (L²)

Acid base properties of L² (isosbestic points) :

The UV-Visible spectra of the indicator L², Fig. 1, in aqueous ethanol for both of their acidic and basic forms show the existence of isosbestic points³ at wave length $\lambda = 406$ nm. This also suggests that the two conjugate acid-base pairs are characterized by their maximum absorbance at 505 nm and 349 nm for indicator L². Extended delocalization in both acid and basic forms of the indicator as observed from Fig. 2, absorbance at 505 nm is observed in all the possible forms. On the other hand, naphtholate group is present in only in strong basic forms. So its absorbance at 349 nm is similar to that of naphtholate ion (345 nm)¹⁴.

Conductometric experiment :

The relevant data is obtained by conductometric titration of a strong acid (HCl) with a strong base (NaOH) in presence of indicator (*E*)-1-(2-(4-hydroxyphenyl)diazenyl)-2-naphthol, L² (1), Methyl orange (2) and phenolphthalein (3) in aqueous solution.

For studying conductometric titration³ an aliquot of 20 ml 0.004 (N) HCl diluted by 80 ml triple-distilled water was taken. After addition of each indicator solution the mixture was titrated with 0.04 (N) NaOH solution added from a micro burette. From a perusal of Fig. 3, it is evident that the colour transition point with the indicator L² is very near to the actual equivalence point found from conductometric titration.

Data analysis and interpretation :

Conductometric equivalence point and the colour transition point for L² (1), Methyl orange (2) and phenolphthalein (3) indicators when conductometric titration of a strong acid (HCl) is carried out with a strong base (NaOH).

Considering conductometric titration as a method for

Fig. 1. UV-Vis spectra of acidic and basic forms of L^2 indicator.

Fig. 2. Delocalization of electrons in both acid and basic forms of L^2 .

analyzing different indicator titration, an error in the volume of titre requirement with respect to the volume required in the conductometric titration, arises as 5% for L^2 , while similar errors is 10% for Methyl orange and 2.5% for phenolphthalein (Fig. 3).

This results reveal that the order of performance among the indicators studied for titration between a strong acid and a strong base is as follows :

Phenolphthalein > L^2 > Methyl orange.

Molar extinction coefficient, ϵ ($M^{-1} cm^{-1}$) :

Molar extinction coefficients, ϵ ($M^{-1} cm^{-1}$) values of (*E*)-1-(2-(4-hydroxyphenyl)diazenyl)-2-naphthol (L^2) in-

dicator was compared³ with a standard indicator like Methyl orange at the λ_{max} (nm) of their acidic and basic forms in Table 5.

Determination of indicator constant (pK_{In}) of indicator, L^2 :

The experimental observations are in agreement with the results reported in IR and UV studies. The pH transition range for change of colour of solution with indicator L^2 8.5–9.2. Thus pH transition range which is nearly 8.8 and pK_{In} value of L^2 is 8.7 at 35 °C, indicate that these reagent are fit to act as indicator³ for titration of strong acid with strong alkali.

Fig. 3. Conductometric titration of a dilute strong acid (HCl) with a dilute strong base (NaOH) in presence of (*E*)-1-(2-(4-hydroxyphenyl)diazenyl)-2-naphthol, L² (1), Methyl orange (2) and phenolphthalein (3) indicators and conductometric end point (4).

Table 5. Molar extinction coefficients, ϵ ($M^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$)

Extreme medium	<i>(E)</i> -1-(2-(4-Hydroxyphenyl)- diazenyl)-2-naphthol (L ²)		Methyl orange	
	$\epsilon \times 10^{-5}$	λ_{max} (nm)	$\epsilon \times 10^{-5}$	λ_{max} (nm)
In alkaline solution	0.091	349	0.203	480
			0.092	515
In acidic solution	0.044	505	0.221	480
			0.369	515

Conclusion

Two novel azo dyes have been synthesized which can be applied in jute dyeing in basic condition. Due to presence of significant antibacterial activity of the dyes, they seem to become an antibacterial useful material after dyeing. In addition, L² shows two stable forms. The colour of one form is light pink ($1 < \text{pH} < 8.5$) having $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 505 \text{ nm}$ and another form is blue ($9.2 < \text{pH} < 13.0$) with $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 349 \text{ nm}$. It shows better performance as an indicator than Methyl orange, particularly in dilute solutions.

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References

- Bradford, Colour Index, 3rd ed. (2nd rev.), 1982, The Society of Dyers and Colourists, USA.
- Opinion of the Scientific Committee on Cosmetic Products and non-food Products intended for Consumers, *The Safety Review of the use of certain azo-dyes in Cosmetic Products*, 2002, **01**, 2.
- K. Pandey, P. Giri, R. Patra, S. K. Bhattacharya and M. B. Saha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2007, **84**, 256.
- K. Pandey, P. Giri, S. Bhattacharya, M. B. Saha, A. Dey and S. N. Chattopadhyay, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2006, **83**, 409.
- J. Sarkhel, S. N. Chattopadhyay, S. K. Bhaduri, T. Deb, K. Pandey and M. B. Saha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2007, **84**, 1020.
- P. K. Saha and M. B. Saha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1995, **72**, 755.
- T. Dev, S. Khamarai, P. S. Guin, M. B. Saha, P. C. Mondal and S. Das, *Int. J. Pure Appl. Chem.*, 2009, **4**, 131.

8. M. Sahu, M. B. Saha and S. C. Bera, *J. Photochem. Photobiol.*, 1995, **89**, 19.
9. John R. Dyer, "Application of Absorption Spectroscopy of Organic Compounds", 6th ed., 1987 (January), p. 37.
10. Robert M. Silverstein and Francis X. Webster, "Spectrometric Identification of Organic Compounds", 6th ed., John Wiley & Sons, Inc, New York, 1996.
11. William Kemp, "Organic Spectroscopy", 3rd ed., Palgrave, New York, 1991.
12. N. Sekar, *Colourage*, 1999, **46**, 63.
13. A. Chakraborty, P. K. Saha, C. Datta, A. R. Das and M. B. Saha, *Colourage*, 2009, **7**, 82.
14. K. M. Solntsen, D. Huppert and N. Agmon, *J. Phys. Chem. (A)*, 1998, **102**, 9599.